

Scoping document

Preliminary assessment of the knowledge gaps to soil pollution and restoration

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Academic editor: Nikolay Mehandzhiyski

Received: 26 Jan 2024 | Accepted: 27 May 2024 | Published: 13 Jun 2024

Citation: Pump J, De Schamphelaere K, Stankovics P, Cioci G, Tóth G (2024) Preliminary assessment of the knowledge gaps to soil pollution and restoration. *Soils for Europe 1*: e119627.

<https://doi.org/10.3897/soils4europe.e119627>

Contributors and Reviewers

We would like to thank all the stakeholders of our Think Tank for their valuable contributions to this scoping document, by providing written or verbal contributions, bilaterally, during organised events online or in person, or during the project meeting in Barcelona in December 2023. We would like to thank Iustina Baoja, Samuel Bickel, Ferenc Gondi, Caroline Heinzl, Karen Louise Johnson, Mellany Klompe, Gerry Lawson, Willem Ravensberg, Vera Silva, Robin Simpson, Felix Wäckers.

We would like to thank all the readers and reviewers of this scoping document for their valuable feedback and suggestions, which we have processed and/or will further consider, process and integrate during the development of the next version of this scoping document, to be expected in September/October 2024. We would like to thank Samuel Bickel, Caroline Heinzl, Karen Louise Johnson, Guusje Koorneef, Karen Naciph, Anna Krzywoszynska, Robin Simpson and Willem Ravensberg.

Abbreviations

EC European Commission

EEA European Environmental Agency

GA General Agreement of the SOLO project (official documentum)

ICM Integrated Crop Management

IPM Integrated Pest Management

JRC Joint Research Centre

LUCAS Land Use and Coverage Area frame Survey

PAH Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons

POPs Persistent Organic Pollutants

PRTT Pollution and Restoration Think Thank

SML Soil Monitoring Law

SUD Sustainable Use of Pesticides

1 Introduction

1.1 Background specific to Pollution and Restoration Think Thank (PRTT)

Soils being largely hidden from view, some of their needs for protection have been unjustifiably overlooked in the EU 'acquis' and in many national bodies of law, being treated as less important than air, water and marine environments. Healthy soils provide a wide variety of ecosystem services, which are also essential to human health, such as biodiversity, nutrient cycling, sustainable plant production, natural pest control, good water quality, water retention, carbon storage and erosion management (GIZ 2021). Soils are estimated to harbour about 59% of Earth's species and possibly more. For example, 90% of fungi, 85% of plants and 50% of bacteria are living in soils (Anthony et al. 2023), and provide the basis for healthy ecosystems and human health (European Commission et al. 2020). Soil pollution is one of the main factors compromising soil health. Soil pollution impacts soil biodiversity and ecosystem services, and impacts human health and well-being.

Due to their strong linkages to environment, nature, biodiversity, ecosystem functioning, agriculture, human and animal health, water and climate, soil pollution and restoration are relevant and connected to a wide framework of EU policies and legislations (European Commission 2023a). Specific EU legislation on soils has been lacking for many years. As part of [The European Green Deal \(europa.eu\)](https://european-council.europa.eu/media/en/press-communications/infographic/infographic-green-deal-2021-11-14-1) and the [Biodiversity strategy for 2030 \(europa.eu\)](https://european-council.europa.eu/media/en/press-communications/infographic/infographic-biodiversity-strategy-2021-11-14-1) (Montanarella and Panagos 2021), an [EU Soil Strategy for 2030](https://european-council.europa.eu/media/en/press-communications/infographic/infographic-soil-strategy-2021-11-14-1) was published in 2021, setting out a framework and measures for the protection, restoration and sustainable use of EU Soils (European Commission et al. 2020). A [linked policy](#)

process for the development of a draft of Soil Law was initiated, leading to the publication of the proposal for an 'EU Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience' ('Soil Monitoring Law', SML) by the European Commission (EC) on 5th of July 2023. There are/have been several EU legislations and proposals that are directly related to the soil policy framework and mentioned as relevant in reaching the main goals. One of them was the proposal of the European Commission on a Sustainable Use of Plant Protection Products Regulation, which would replace the current Directive on Sustainable Use of Pesticides (SUD). The proposal aimed to reduce the use and risk of pesticides by 50% by 2030, a goal of the Farm to Fork Strategy, and lead to the effective implementation of Integrated Pest Management. However, the proposal was rejected by the European Parliament in November 2023, and retraced by the European Commission in February 2024. Although Integrated Pest Management (IPM) has been mandatory since 2014 under SUD, implementation in member states has been lacking (*European Court of Auditors 2020, European Parliamentary Research Service 2018, European Commission 2020b*). The SUR proposal aimed at tackling the lack of implementation of the current Directive. It is currently unclear if and when, under the new Commission after the European elections in June 2024, a new proposal for a Regulation on pesticide use will be published.

The two main guiding documents setting the policy frameworks for soil and directly addressing soil pollution are

1. the Implementation Plan of the Soil Mission, which is also an important component of the European Green Deal (European Commission 2021b) and
2. EU Action Plan: 'Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil' (European Commission 2021a). As part of the EU's zero pollution ambition, the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability Towards a Toxic Free Environment was also developed (European Commission 2020a).

These policy documents specify the problem areas regarding soil health, (polluting economic sectors/activities and polluting agents) and identify targets, based on assessments of the state of the art regarding soil health, identified needs and feasibility of reaching specific goals. One of the outcomes of the implementation of these elements is the Soil Monitoring Law (SML) proposal. The aim of the SML proposal, published by the EC and currently under negotiation in the Council, after which trilogues among the Commission, the Parliament and the Council will take place, is to be a cornerstone in reaching the objectives of the EU Soil Strategy for 2030 and the Soil Mission. The SML proposal is much needed and widely welcomed, however, was also criticised by scientists, civil society and drinking water companies (Wageningen University 2023a, EEB 2023, EurEau 2023) regarding notable shortcomings. Since it does not address all goals and targets identified in the policy documents, an improvement of the proposal and/or further legislative proposals are needed in order to reach healthy soils by 2050. The lack of clear rules and objectives, the lack of focus on soil biodiversity and diffuse pollution and the lack of linkages with water pollution and legislation, have been identified as essential shortcomings of the proposal by the scientific community (EEB 2023, EurEau 2023, Wageningen University 2023b). Moreover, during the plenary vote in the European Parliament in April 2024, essential provisions of the proposal were drastically watered

down, further compromising the potential impact of the proposal (European Environmental Bureau 2024).

The current PRTT used the problem areas described in these documents as a starting point to identify the state-of-the-art and knowledge gaps, and to provide input for roadmap co-development. The PRTT will focus on soil pollution, soil restoration and remediation, while also taking into account the impact on, and of, soil pollution regarding connected systems such as crops and plant vegetation, water bodies (groundwater, surface water), air, (air or water born pollution or pollution through leaching and volatilization processes) and overall ecosystem health and ecosystem functioning.

1.2 Scope (specific to PRTT)

The above two strategic documents set specific targets related to soil pollution.

As a basis, the PRTT aims to provide a state-of-the-art and an assessment of knowledge gaps, potential (innovative) solutions and actionable research regarding formulated goal's objectives, targets and indicators based on the two main policy documents. PRTT will address the complexity of the issues involved in soil pollution and reflect on their intertwined nature by highlighting the need for a holistic approach and integration of soil aspects to all relevant policies. (The need for such an approach is well demonstrated by the Impact Assessment Report accompanying the SML.) It is important to identify policy areas that are directly linked to soil pollution, because the various policy instruments used in those fields do have an intentional or unintentional impact on pollution that should not be ignored but explored through well defined research questions.

Table 1 below indicates the concrete Targets, Baseline and Soil health indicators of the Soil Mission to be achieved by 2030 viewed as capable of contributing to meet the 2050 target: soil pollution is reduced to levels no longer considered harmful to health and natural ecosystems (European Commission 2021b, p. 16). The listed targets and indicators of the Soil Mission do not address all pollution problems identified in the Support Material, nor those in the Zero Pollution Action Plan as it is demonstrated by the background working documents of the Soil Monitoring Law. While the targets, baselines and indicators are clear reflections on the intention to reduce pollution to a level that is no longer harmful to soil, health and natural ecosystems, there are some aspects that need further clarification to make the targets operational such as baseline year for calculating percentages. In some cases these negotiations have been already taking place outside of the soil mission (e.g. the reduction of the use of pesticides) which demonstrates the interlinkages and intertwined nature of the various policies.

2 State-of-the-Art

The state-of-the-art in the soil pollution and restoration domain will be further reviewed during the next phase of the project. In this chapter, we lay down the principles and

methods to develop a comprehensive overview of the domain, and provide a first summary of relevant available knowledge and literature.

Table 1. Targets and proposed soil health indicators for the mission objective: <i>Reduce pollution and enhance restoration in the Soil Mission Implementation Plan.</i>		
Mission targets in line with EU and global commitment	Baseline	Soil health indicators
1: reduce the overall use and risk of chemical pesticides by 50% and the use of more hazardous pesticides by 50% 2: reducing fertilizer use by at least 20% 3: reduce nutrient losses by at least 50% 4: 25% of land under organic farming 5: Reduce microplastics released to soils to meet 30% target of zero pollution action plan 6: Halt and reduce secondary Salinization	27% - 31% of land with excess nutrient pollution Soil contamination: 2.5% (non-agricultural), 21% (conventional arable), ca. 40-80% of land from atmospheric deposition depending on the pollutant. Farmland under organic agriculture: 8.5% (2019)	Presence of soil pollutants, excess nutrients and salts

Source: Soil Mission Implementation Plan, p 16

2.1 System-approach and conceptual framework

A system-approach was developed to comprehensively tackle all aspects of the soil pollution and soil restoration/remediation domain by using the above-mentioned documents as a starting point, literature review listed under Reference and the feed-backs from our stakeholders, as explained under domain 3 below. The following studies provided more input for the development of the system-approach framework shown in Fig. 1: Adhikari and Hartemink 2016, Babí Almenar et al. 2021, Bouma 2014, Greiner et al. 2017, Jónsson and Davíðsdóttir 2016, Lacalle et al. 2020, O’Riordan 2021, Pulleman et al. 2012, Stolte 2016, Vári et al. 2021, Velasquez and Lavelle 2019, Villa et al. 2014, Stavi et al. 2016, Dushkova et al. 2021, Wade 2022, JRC and Maes 2020, Ponge 2015, Wood and Blankinship 2022. Putting soil health into the centre of the system-approach allows us to highlight all elements that are relevant for reaching the Soil Mission objectives of 2050, to demonstrate the complexity of pollution issues including the intertwined nature of policies and to provide a framework for assessing the state-of-the-art, the knowledge gaps and to identify key research questions. A schematic overview of this system approach and the components of the system are presented in Fig. 1. Three main domains were identified as pollution relevant during the scoping process along with the principles that should be integrated into all domains, since they reflect on pollution relevant social and economic aspects.

Figure 1. [doi](#)

Concept overview of System approach to identify interlinkages between domains related to soil pollution/contamination (created by the PRTT).

The four domains:

1. **Soil pollution:** identification and assessment of the extent of polluting agricultural and non-agricultural human activities and pollutants including (i) inorganic, (ii) organic) (also living organism) based on (i) soil descriptors and (ii) criteria reflecting on soil health
2. **Effects of pollution:** identification and assessment of extent of the impact of soil pollution on i) soil properties and conditions including linkages with other polluting pathways, ii) ecosystem services, soil functions and biodiversity and iii) human livelihoods. Negatively affected (directly or indirectly), (ii) Beneficiaries of polluting activities (e.g. polluters and clean-up companies)
3. **Solutions to soil pollution:** Identification of availability of and need for both solutions focused on (i) pollution prevention and (ii) restoration and remediation, as well as the assessment of the role of different stakeholders and policy decisions/frameworks in view of (implementation of) solutions. Negatively affected (directly or indirectly), (ii) Beneficiaries of polluting activities (e.g. polluters and clean-up companies), (iii) Stakeholders influencing decision making (science, business, civil society, consumers), (iv) Decision makers. Individual stakeholders or groups of stakeholders can belong to one or to all of mentioned categories.

The Principles for reaching soil pollution reduction targets (2030 and 2050):

- **Fairness and equality:** distribution of and access to natural resources should be fair providing equal opportunity to everyone
- **Intergenerational justice:** refers to the close relationship between generations and mutual respect (Rockström et al. 2023)

- **Precautionary Principle:** allows measures to be taken to avoid risk of environmental harm, even in the face of scientific uncertainty
- **Prevention Principle:** allows preventive measures to prevent the occurrence of environmental damage
- **Polluter Pays Principle:** costs related to environmental damage should be born by those who caused it
- **Public Participation:** the public is involved and is given early and effective opportunities to participate in all stages of their elaboration, when all options are still open
- **Eco-Economic Decoupling:** breaking the links between economic growth and environmental pressure

2.2 Summary of State of the Art on Soil Pollution and Restoration

This part provides a first summary of relevant available knowledge and literature in the domain of soil pollution and restoration, based on a first set of relevant literature and inputs of stakeholders gathered so-far. The state-of-the art will be further developed during the next phase of the project. Specifically, the state-of-the art will be strengthened with a further review of key relevant grey and scientific literature, as well as with information and outcomes from relevant projects, including the SMS, Prep Soil and EJP soil project.

2.2.1 Sources and scope of soil pollution

In this section, a first overview is given of important factors contributing to soil pollution. This overview will be extended and further elaborated during the following phases of the project. In section 2.2.2 and 2.2.3, a first summary of important impacts of soil pollution is provided. Two main types of soil pollution are mostly considered in literature: point-source soil pollution and diffuse soil pollution.

Point-source soil pollution

Point-source soil pollution is associated with 'contaminated sites', which include sites where accidental or intentional spillage took place, and current or former industrial, waste disposal, mining, transport infrastructure and storage sites. Inorganic and organic pollutants, heavy metals, Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) and Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAH) are pollutants often involved in point-source soil pollution. Point-source pollution also frequently involves historic contamination. Current available data on the number and the areal extent of contaminated sites in the EU are characterised by large knowledge gaps. The JRC estimated in 2018 that EU-28 counted about 2.8 million potentially polluted sites: sites where polluting activities are taking place or took place (Paya Perez and E.N. 2018). An EEA report published in 2022, based on national registries, showed that in 2016 1.38 million potentially contaminated sites were registered. About two third of contaminated sites could be potentially historic (e.g. brownfields) (EEA 2022). In 2016, 115 000 contaminated soils were estimated to be remediated in the EU; about 8.3% of the currently registered potentially contaminated sites . It is estimated that at

least 166 000 additional sites are in need for remediation or measures which reduce risk (EEA 2022, European Commission 2023a) . Historic contaminated sites don't fall under current legislation regarding industrial pollution prevention, such as for example the Industrial Emissions Directive. The proposal of the European Commission for the SML, currently under negotiation in the EU Parliament and Council, does include provisions on identification, assessment and management of contaminated sites, and aims to at least partly fill this policy gap. Also data on remediation of contaminated sites are scarce/limited.

Diffuse Soil Pollution

Diffuse soil pollution involves soil pollution whereby matter is transported under a gradient of chemical potential, activity or concentration that often spreads over large areas, and in general doesn't originate from an easily identifiable, single source. These characteristics cause important challenges in assessing the full scope of diffuse soil pollution. Diffuse pollution often leads to chronic exposure to lower concentrations of pollutants, while the health and ecotoxicological impact of chronic exposure are more difficult to assess, and have been less researched. Agro-chemicals, fertilizers and manure are important contributors to diffuse soil pollution, as well as road traffic and the diffusion of point-source pollution. Often, diffuse soil pollution is further transported by air and water. Important diffuse soil contaminants are listed below (Paya Perez and E.N. 2018,IUNG 2019, Rodríguez-Eugenio et al. 2018).

Pesticides

Agro-chemical soil pollution, including pesticides, has been identified as a major soil threat (Stolte 2016). Different studies, among more by Orton et al. (2013), Pose-Juan et al. (2015), Qu et al. (2016), Chiaia-Hernandez et al. (2017), Hvězdová et al. (2018), have already provided data on the distribution of currently approved or banned pesticides in soils. However, a comprehensive overview on pesticide residues in the soils in the EU has been lacking due to different methods and analyte lists, and different sampling periods and strategies used among different studies. On the contrary, data on pesticide residues in surface water are more abundant, through monitoring in framework of the Water Framework Directive, and additional monitoring in some member states. For example, in the Netherlands pesticide spills in surface water have been monitored for many years (Institute of Environmental Sciences (CML), Leiden University and Royal HaskoningDHV 2024).

An important source of information on the presence of pesticide residues in European soils is the work of Silva et al. (Silva et al. 2022, Silva et al. 2019, Silva et al. 2023, Silva 2022). A large-scale study analyzing 76 pesticide residues in 317 EU agricultural top soils showed that 83% of soils contained 1 or more residues, while 58% of soils contained mixtures of different pesticides (Silva et al. 2019). A large scale study in framework of the H2020 SPRINT project umbrella assessed the presence and levels of 209 pesticide residues in 625 environmental samples in different matrices (soil, crop, outdoor air, indoor dust, surface water and sediment), across 10 study sites (Silva et al. 2023). In 86% of the complete set of samples at least one residue was measured, and in 76% of samples mixtures of different pesticides residues were found. 201 of the samples were taken in

soils, and revealed 100 different pesticides. In soils of conventional farms, 99% of the samples contained pesticides, while 96% contained mixtures of at least two pesticide residues. For soils of organic farms, these numbers were 95% and 79% respectively. Total concentrations of pesticides in conventional fields reached a max value of 28.678 ug/kg, and 5.458 ug/kg in organic soils. The study of Silva et al. (Silva et al. 2019) made use of 317 samples from the 2015 LUCAS survey (Land Use and Coverage Area frame Survey). The 2018 LUCAS program included a pesticide module, which will probably be extended (Orgiazzi et al. 2022, Vieira et al. 2023).

Although still limited, the available data show that mixtures of pesticide residues are the rule rather than the exception. Large-scale, harmonized monitoring of mixtures of pesticides residues is urgently needed to evaluate risk for ecosystem and human health (Silva et al. 2023).

Limited data is available on the actual application of pesticides, which will change with the implementation of the Regulation on Statistics on agricultural inputs and outputs (European Commission 2022b). Pesticide sales data, a proxy for actual applications, show that pesticide use has increased from about 215 000 tonnes (2011) tot more than 345 000 tonnes (2017) (Eurostat 2022a).

Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs)

Important sources of Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) are emissions from agriculture, combustion and industry, and from disposed commercial products (e.g. plastic containing POPs). The waste sector is relevant for the more recent POPs, for example through application of sludge. Data on POPs pollution of soils are very limited. For example, a EU study from 2011 (European Commission 2011) included only limited data on 4 POPs pollutants in soils. Under the Stockholm Convention, data on POPs for 2021 (UNEP 2021) were gathered, however important data gaps remain. Long-term POPs pollution trends have shown no decline in Benzo(a)pyrene (B(a)p) air pollution and high concentrations of polychlorinated dioxines and furans (PCDD/Fs) in Europe (TF HTAP 2021).

Also for emerging contaminants, such as the widely used Perfluoralkyl chemicals (PFASs), an important lack of data exists. PFASs resist degradation, and are easily transported over long distances. PFASs pollution is widespread, including in soils, water and waste. Remediation of sites polluted with PFASs is technically challenging and costly (Council of the European Union 2019).

Pharmaceuticals (including veterinary products) and personal care products

An estimated 5,507.4 tonnes of active substance of antimicrobial Veterinary Medicinal Products were sold in Europe in 2020 (EU-27, UK, Iceland, Norway and Switzerland). In the period 2011-2020, a decrease of 43.2% was reported in sales of the 25 countries providing annual data to the European Medicines Agency (European Medicines Agency 2021). Through manure application, veterinary products end up in the soil (Gros et al. 2019), while pharmaceutical and personal care products can pollute soils through sewage sludge application (Gworek et al. 2021). No comprehensive data exist on the scale of

contamination of these contaminants in the EU. For example, the continuous release of antibiotics into the environment is of important concern. The majority of antibiotics are not completely metabolised in humans and animals, and a high percentage is discharged into water and soil through animal manure, municipal wastewater, sewage sludge and biosolids. Antimicrobial drug resistance (AMR) poses an important challenge (Cycoń et al. 2019).

Plastics and microplastics

Available data from Eurostat (Eurostat 2022b) indicate that the generation of plastic was increasing during the past years (9.5 million tonnes (2004) to 17.2 million tonnes (2018)). This entails important potential impacts for soils. For example, the use of plastic in agriculture (e.g. plastic mulching (estimated rate of 100 000 tonnes per year in the EU), plastic in fertilizer products and pesticides, plastic used in greenhouses, crop protection nets, irrigation systems, sports fields with artificial grass,...)) contributes to soil pollution (EIP AGRI 2020). Microplastics waste has also been increasing due to the use in e.g. cosmetics, leading to the widespread presence of microplastics in the environment and in food. Comprehensive data on microplastics are limited. A study (Lofty et al. 2022) estimated that the contribution of microplastics to soils in Europe through sewage sludge is about 31 000 to 42 000 tonnes yearly. Also tyre wear is estimated to be an important source of microplastic pollution, resulting in about 57 3000-65400 tonnes yearly in soils near roads in Germany (Baensch-Baltruschat et al. 2021.)

Nutrients

About 67% of ecosystem areas in Europe are estimated to be exposed to excessive nitrogen. The primary cause is fertiliser use, livestock density and degraded soils in agriculture (European Environment Agency 2018, European Environment Agency 2019, Velthof et al. 2011). Also phosphorus has accumulated in agricultural soils in Europe, after the introduction of phosphorus-containing fertilizers in addition to manure. Manure can also be a source of antibiotics from veterinary medicines (Antikainen et al. 2008, Panagos et al. 2022).

Heavy metals

European countries have a number of approaches to define risk levels associated with different concentrations of heavy metal in soil (Carlon et al., 2007; Ferguson, 1999). The Finnish standard values represent a good approximation of the mean values of different national systems in Europe (Carlon et al., 2007) and India (Awasthi, 2000) and they have been applied in an international context for agricultural soils as well (UNEP, 2013).

About 6.24% of EU agricultural area is estimated to contain high concentrations of heavy metals (concentration above the guideline value set by the Finnish legislation for contaminated soils in agricultural areas) (Ministry of the Environment, Finland 2007). Copper, lead and zinc are estimated to be accumulating in EU soils, while for cadmium a net decline is estimated (De Vries et al. 2022). High concentrations of copper are found in vineyards and orchards in humid climates, because of a high use of fungicides (Ballabio et

al. 2018). Ballabio et al. 2021 found that EU hotspots of mercury are located close to mine areas, coal-fired power plants and chlor-alkali industries.

Beyond agricultural soils, data on heavy metals are limited. Panagos et al. (2021) estimated that the average concentration of mercury in EU top soils amounted to 103 g/ha. About 6 tonnes per year would be transferred downstream via transport of sediments (EU27 + UK). Tóth et al. (2016) indicated that heavy metal concentrations in soils are very unevenly distributed through the EU, with many sites of highly concentrated pollution.

Pourret and Hursthouse (2019) (Pourret and Hursthouse 2019) have suggested to use the term 'Potentially Toxic Elements' instead of 'heavy metals' when reporting environmental research. During our further work within the Tink Thank, we will explore this option.

Waste management and disposal

Waste management and disposal (e.g. sewage sludge, water purification, (urban) compost has a direct and important link with soil pollution. In the further development of the scoping document, this topic will be further elaborated on in both the state of the art as the knowledge gaps.

2.2.2 Impacts of soil pollution on biodiversity and ecosystems

Different studies have indicated important negative impacts of soil pollution on ecosystems and their services (water purification, water retention, food production, biodiversity, etc.) (Morgado et al. 2018, Rodríguez-Eugenio et al. 2018).

For example, pesticide residues in soil hold risk for biodiversity, ecosystems and their services, and get transported to/taken up by other matrices (water, air, indoor dust, food, microorganisms/microbiota, animals, humans, ...). Many pesticide residues are persistent, bioaccumulative or toxic to non-target species (Silva et al. 2019, Silva et al. 2023.) Pesticide residues in soil are shown to negatively impact soil macroorganisms microbiota and the microbiome, as described in a review of Gunstone et al. 2021 on the negative impacts of pesticides on beneficial soil-dwelling invertebrates. Pesticide pollution in soils can alter processes in the rhizosphere, impact plant growth and resistance against pests, alter the composition of soil microorganisms, and can lead to an increase of pathogens and decrease of beneficial organisms. Also changes in nutrient composition in roots, leaves, grape juice and xylem sap have been observed after pesticide applications (Klátyik et al. 2023, Mandl et al. 2018, Zobiolo et al. 2010, Zaller et al. 2018, Brühl and Zaller 2021, Ruuskanen et al. 2023). Negative effects on soil organisms also impact fauna dependent on soil organisms, e.g. farmland birds (Rigal et al. 2023).

The excess of fertilizer and manure cause extensive negative impacts on waterways and biodiversity. E.g. mycorrhizal fungi, essential for many soil functions and services, are negatively affected by excessive nutrients (Origiazzi 2016). The multifunctionality of soils, and the trade-offs between for excess nutrients and other soil functions, are assessed by Vazquez et al. 2020.

Pharmaceuticals, such as antibiotics, can affect soil microorganisms, for example by changing their enzyme activity and ability to metabolize different carbon sources, and by altering the overall microbial biomass and relative abundance of different groups (Cycoń et al. 2019).

Microplastics can impact soil physicochemical properties (e.g. increase bulk density, decrease porosity and water holding capacity), soil microorganisms, macro-organisms, plant growth and can leach toxic chemicals (Lofty et al. 2022).

Although negative (potential) impacts of different soil pollutants on biodiversity and ecosystem functioning have been shown by a variety of studies, the complete and long-term impact of the cumulative effects of different soil pollutants on the variety of different organisms exposed remains unknown. In general, there is a lack of long-term studies that also evaluate the impact of mixtures and cumulative effects on a wide range of organisms and ecosystem services.

In the next phase of the development of this scoping document, an overview table of the main described (potential) impacts of soil pollutants on biodiversity and ecosystems described in literature will be summarised.

2.2.3 Impacts of soil pollution on stakeholders

Different studies have indicated that soil pollution directly affects human health. Soil pollution can contaminate food, which can pose risks for human health. Many links have been described between increased risks for a variety of illnesses and health impacts, and pollutants frequently found in soils, such as arsenic, lead, and cadmium, organic chemicals such as PCBs (polychlorinated biphenyls), PAHs (polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons), pharmaceuticals such as antibiotics, pesticides and micro-plastics (Rodríguez-Eugenio et al. 2018, Cox et al. 2019, European Commission 2019, Lim 2021). Rodríguez-Eugenio et al. 2018 underline the potential risks of contaminated soil for human health, including uptake from dust and vapours by farm workers, skin contact and ingestion of soil.

Tolerable daily intake values for pesticide residues are likely to underestimate the risk to consumers, as they don't account for mixture effects (Silva et al. 2019). Pathways other than ingestion or food, such as inhalation or skin contact, are seriously underestimated. Soil pollutants, such as pesticide residues, can accumulate in the lighter top layer of the soil, and easily get transported by the wind and inhaled by animals and humans. Pesticide residues have also been shown to accumulate in indoor dust (Silva et al. 2019, Silva et al. 2023, Silva et al. 2022, Navarro et al. 2023). A recent paper by Matsuzaki et al. 2023 highlights the potential links between pesticide exposure and the microbiota-gut-brain axis.

Overall, there is an important lack of research on the potential long-term impacts of mixtures of soil pollutants people are exposed to. Here the "exposome" is relevant: the measure of all the exposures of an individual throughout a lifetime and how those exposures relate to health. There is also an important link between the impact of soil pollutants on (soil) biodiversity and human health, as soil pollutants can lead to the

selection for harmful taxa and to an overall decrease in diversity of microbiota, also leading to effects on the human microbiome. More and more research also refers to the impacts of soil pollutants on the gut microbiome, and potential links with health conditions, including neurological illnesses. Soil pollutants can lead to advantages for harmful microbiota, for example through antibiotics resistance (Roslund et al. 2024).

Soil pollution is associated with important economic and social impacts and costs. For example, soil pollution can negatively impact health, land availability, water quality, water retention, crop growth/food production and other ecosystem services (Bouma 2014, Adhikari and Hartemink 2016, Greiner et al. 2017, Jónsson and Davíðsdóttir 2016, JRC and Maes 2020, Lacalle et al. 2020, O'Riordan 2021, Pulleman et al. 2012, Stavi et al. 2016, Stolte 2016, Velasquez and Lavelle 2019).

In the next phase of the development of this scoping document, an overview table of the main described (potential) impacts of soil pollutants on stakeholders described in literature will be summarised.

2.2.4 Solutions to soil pollution

Prevention of soil pollution

Agriculture

Different practices and management tools are available to decrease soil pollution. Integrated Pest Management (IPM), Integrated Crop Management (ICM) and agro-ecological practices have been shown to provide effective approaches to minimizing inputs of pesticides and fertilizers, and maximizing ecosystem functioning and services, such as biological pest control. These approaches are based on increasing the resilience of the crop, while agro-chemicals such as pesticides are only used as a last resort, if needed, instead of prophylactic or calendar-based practices (Rodríguez-Eugenio et al. 2018, IPM Works 2022). Different EU legislations and initiatives are in force or in development which can contribute to reduction of soil pollution originating from agricultural activities. An assessment of these legislations, their expected impacts and limitations, will be carried out in the next phase of the project.

Non-agricultural soil pollution

Different EU legislations and initiatives are in force or in development which can contribute to reduction of soil pollution originating from industry, traffic and waste. An assessment of these legislations, their expected impacts and limitations, will be carried out in the next phase of the project.

Remediation of soil pollution

Remediation techniques are often divided into in situ (on the site) and ex situ (off the site) remediation, and include physical, chemical and biological treatments. Physicochemical treatments are often characterized with high speed and efficiency, but also with high costs

and labour, and potential destruction of soil functionality. The field of remediation techniques has developed over time to a focus on effective restoration of soil quality and preservation of the environment, while minimizing the damage caused by clean-up interventions. Recent developments have also reflected the aim to promote clean-up strategies which also address climate change effects (Grifoni et al. 2022). Biological treatments provide eco-friendly features and larger social acceptance, but often require long periods. A wide variety of biological techniques have been developed and successfully applied. Lacalle et al. 2020 provide an overview of biological methods of polluted soil remediation for an effective economically-optimal recovery of soil health and ecosystem services. Methods include phytoremediation, phytoextraction, phytostabilization, phytomanagement, bioremediation and vermiremediation. Specific challenges are associated with soils contaminated with multiple pollutants. For example the interaction between organic and inorganic pollutants can change bioaccessibility and solubility of pollutants and their biotoxicity and biological metabolic processes. For pollutants that are relatively new to the environment, such as PFAS, important challenges remain due to unknown pathways of degradation. Also competition or joint-adsorption on binding sites poses a challenge. For mixed contaminated soils, successful combinations of chemical and biological remediation techniques have been discussed, although more research is needed (Aparicio et al. 2022, Lacalle et al. 2020). More research is needed on the potential of nature-based solutions and the use of microorganisms for bioremediation processes. In general, more research is needed to improve efficiency, feasibility, costs and time-efficiency of remediation techniques for a variety of different contaminants and soil conditions. As mentioned in the document, this is a significant knowledge gap (Grifoni et al. 2022, Aparicio et al. 2022, Huysegoms and Cappuyns 2017, Lacalle et al. 2020, Ministry of the Environment, Finland 2007, Mulligan et al. 2001, Smith 2010).

In the next phase of the development of this scoping document, an overview table of the main (potential) technical solutions (related to prevention and remediation) to soil pollution described in literature will be summarised.

2.2.5 Social and economic tools to prevent soil pollution/fitness-for-purpose

Important reoccurring aspects regarding socio-economic and market tools relevant to tackling soil pollution are the need for implementation of the polluter pays principle, as well as for the targeted use of public funds. For example, current agricultural legislation and funding doesn't secure linkages between funding and protection of the environment and enhancement of ecosystem services (OECD 2023). The polluter pays principle is insufficiently included in legislation, while the loss of ecosystem services associated with soil degradation is not integrated into economic optimisation of economic actors. Historic soil pollution poses an additional problem, which challenges the implementation of the polluter pays principle. Who should cover remediation costs of historic pollution remains often a challenge (European Commission 2023a). An important potential instruments is a pollution levy, e.g. a pesticide levy, which is for example used in Denmark (Nielsen et al. 2023). Austria has, for example, a well-designed tax on landfill, incineration and other

forms of waste disposal: the waste disposal tax (Altlastenbeitrag) (European Commission 2021c).

In the next phase of the development of this scoping document, an overview table of the main (potential) social and economic tools to reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration will be summarised.

2.2.6 Lock-in mechanisms of soil pollution

Soil pollution is associated with many "lock-in mechanisms". Lock-in mechanisms can be described as the barriers and underlying mechanisms that are holding back the transition towards decreasing or preventing soil pollution. For example, the lock-in mechanisms of pesticide use were analyzed elaborately in the framework of [the Sprint project](#) (Frelilh-Larsen and Sprint project 2022). These lock-in mechanisms include factors related to farmer's perceptions and views (Vanino et al. 2022), agronomy and research, economics, knowledge and awareness and policy and regulation. For example, lack of linkage between Common Agricultural Policy funding and the implementation of Integrated Pest Management (IPM)/Integrated Crop Management (ICM), lack of the Common Agricultural Policy and soil health, lack of independent advisory systems, consumer awareness or market outlets for alternative crops contribute to lock-in mechanisms. Lock-in mechanisms contributing to soil pollution will be further explored during the analysis of 'bottlenecks' in reducing soil pollution and restoration.

In the next phase of the development of this scoping document, an overview table of the main lock-in mechanisms challenging reducing soil pollution and enhancing restoration will be summarised.

3. Knowledge Gaps

This chapter provides a first overview of identified knowledge gaps regarding soil pollution and restoration. In the first part, a schematic overview is provided of key identified knowledge gaps, divided into 4 thematic categories. A second part elaborates on the identified knowledge gaps, and is accompanied by an excel table in Annex, which includes the described knowledge gaps and their mutual links. In a third part, concrete examples of research gaps, focusing specifically on pesticides as an example of soil pollution are given, to further clarify identified knowledge gaps.

3.1 Schematic appraisal of important identified research gaps

The PRTT carried out a first appraisal of knowledge gaps regarding soil pollution and restoration, which will be continued during further steps. This activity exists of an assessment of available knowledge gaps reviews, making use of findings of former relevant projects, a review of a selection of key grey and scientific literature, as well as already identified gaps and needs by the PRTT and stakeholders involved. Fig. 2 provides a first selection of key identified knowledge gaps, divided into four groups: "Definitions,

scope, sources and loads of soil pollution”, “Affected soil properties, ecosystem services and impacts on livelihoods”, “Affected/Involved stakeholders and their role” and “Solutions to soil pollution and needed conditions”.

Figure 2. [doi](#)

Overview of preliminary identified knowledge gaps regarding soil pollution and restoration.

3.2 Description of identified Knowledge Gaps

3.2.1 Knowledge gaps concerning the definition, scope, sources and loads of soil pollution

1 Need for clear definitions regarding soil pollution

A clear definition of soil health, including a clear set of parameters and monitoring approaches is essential. In general, across different studies, projects and policy frameworks, there are different definitions and understandings of ‘soil pollution’. In view of policy frameworks, setting targets and progressing towards targets, there is a need for clear agreements on definitions. For example, the term ‘pollutant’ should be clearly defined, as there is a need to differentiate substances which are causing harm/negative impacts, from those which are present without causing harm. For example substances added to the soil which are causing no harm could be considered contaminants. Substances that are causing negative impacts could be described as pollutants. There should also be made a distinction between naturally present and human introduced pollutants, especially in terms of solutions related to prevention and legislation. However,

also naturally present pollutants, such as heavy metals, can occur at hazardous concentrations (e.g. radon from bedrock in mountainous regions). A clear definition on a 'clean soil' is lacking (FAO 2020): there is no clear understanding on what is considered a clean soil and a polluted soil. For example, should the definition of a clean or healthy soil entail the absence of pollutants/the lack of exceedance of defined concentration thresholds, or the absence of negative impacts on certain soil health descriptors and ecosystem functioning? The thresholds from which certain pollutants are considered harmful depend on the soil characteristics, and are hence often country/region specific.

In view of policy frameworks and projects, there also is a need to define which soil pollutants are considered (e.g. pesticides, potassium, nitrate, mineral oil hydrocarbons, pharmaceuticals, microplastics, PFAS, newly emerging contaminants). A clear classification and prioritization approach is needed, in view of monitoring, setting targets and implementing management practices. In this regard, we also refer to the knowledge gaps on monitoring, indicators and thresholds/criteria.

2 Data gaps on soil pollution in soils and lack of systemized monitoring

A clear lack of data on soil pollution exists, linked to a lack of systemized monitoring frameworks, which are needed to assess the scope and possible impacts of soil pollution, and to develop management and policy tools.

In this regard, it is also needed to (further) develop classification frameworks for contaminants in combination with prioritization methodologies. A classification framework (e.g. decision tree) should take into account:

- The (eco)toxicity of contaminants and impact on soil health, ecosystem functioning and human health, determined by risk assessments. The interaction of the contaminant with other soil substances (e.g. other contaminants, organic matter, clay content) and living organisms. Mixture, synergistic and cumulative effects should be considered
- The prevalence of the contaminants
- Origin of contaminants
- Their persistence (short/medium/long term) and bioaccumulation
- Prevention and Bioremediation solutions
- Possible migration, evaporation and chemical phase change of contaminants of pollutants
- Risk for exposure
- ...

The above criteria should also be considered to develop a set of soil pollution indicators. A contamination framework is essential for improved monitoring and remediation of soil contaminants, and should be taken into account when designing monitoring frameworks, performing risk assessments and setting policy and management priorities.

Also the difficulty of monitoring substances should be taken into account. There is much diversity and complexity in the monitoring of different pollutants. For example, microplastics are very challenging to monitor. Also newly emerging pollutants present an important challenge. It is key to include newly emerging pollutants in monitoring frameworks, for example through generic chemical screening methodologies. Although prioritization approaches and practical feasibility are prerequisites for effective gathering of data and monitoring, it is overall essential to monitor as many soil components/contaminants as possible. Materials which are currently not considered pollutants, could pose extensive problems in the future. Past experience has shown a long delay between substances ending up in soils, and the realisation of their negative impacts, resulting in far-reaching, long-term challenges for ecosystems, their services and human health. Currently there is a lack of understanding of the scope of contaminants/pollutants, including newly emerging contaminants, and their possible (future) impact on soil functioning. Large data gaps exist regarding the presence of emerging pollutants (e.g. pharmaceuticals, endocrine disruptors, hormones, micropollutants (e.g. microplastics) in soils, their behaviour in the environment and their toxicity, transport and bioaccumulation properties in humans. Available research shows that emerging pollutants can raise pollutants of concern, involving high risks for the environment and human health (Rodríguez-Eugenio et al. 2018, Covaci et al. 2011). Enhancing and implementing methodologies to measure and predict the presence and impact of newly emerging contaminants are needed. Concluding, there is a significant need for the development of the appropriate monitoring frameworks and the standardisation of methodologies for the measurement of emerging pollutants.

3 Behaviour/transportation and fate of soil pollutants and link of soil pollution with water and air

Extensive knowledge gaps exist concerning the partition of pollutants in different physical phases, and the behaviour, transportation and fate of many soil pollutants in soil, water and air. For example, transport of pollutants via air, water and soils is a major factor in (diffuse) soil pollution. These three compartments hence need to be adequately assessed to evaluate (the impact of) diffuse soil pollution, demanding complex analyses (Geissen et al. 2021). Soil pollution is a major cause of groundwater and surface water contamination, and NO_x soil emissions can have important impacts on air quality. Local pollution (e.g. contaminated sites) is via transportation processes also often linked to diffuse pollution. At the same time, pollutants found in water bodies and in the air can be transported to soils, through precipitation or deposition processes. The interlinkages of the different matrices entail important consequences for management of pollution. For example, when groundwater is contaminated, the costs and complexity of bioremediation of soils are greatly increased.

Processes of transportation (e.g. wind erosion) and air-water-soil interactions are highly dependent on soil characteristics and climatic conditions. Hence, a global approach is challenging, and site-specific evaluations are needed.

3.2.2 Knowledge gaps concerning affected soil properties, biodiversity, ecosystem functioning and services

4 Impact of soil pollutants (individual and mixtures, short-term and long-term) on soils and soil ecosystem services

Significant knowledge gaps exist concerning the impact of soil pollutants on soil characteristics, including on soil biodiversity, soil functioning, other living organisms and the delivery of ecosystem services.

For the majority of pollutants, there are no comprehensive (eco)toxicity data, and hence risk assessments, available (e.g. microplastics). When data on toxicity and risk are available, they are often limited to the impact of a single pollutant on a small set of organisms during a short time frame, often in controlled (laboratory) conditions. However, it is essential that cumulative and synergistic effects and long-term effects of pollutants in field conditions are taken into account, to assess the probable impacts of soil pollution on long term soil health and ecosystem functioning. Although available research clearly shows the extensive impacts and possible impacts of soil pollution on soil characteristics, biodiversity and the delivery of ecosystem services, large data gaps remain. The high complexity of soil and interactions of soil compounds, organisms and contaminants provides a large challenge in assessing the full impact of soil pollution on the delivery of ecosystem services.

Again, it is important to note that the impacts of soil pollutants are site specific, as they depend on soil characteristics and environmental conditions.

5 Overall impact of soil pollution on wider ecosystem functioning (beyond soils)

On the one hand, soil pollution impacts the ecosystem services directly linked to soils, such as soil biodiversity at all levels (from micro- to macro-organisms), structure, aeration, control of erosion, nutrient cycling, water retention and buffering, crop health and growth, ... On the other hand, soil pollution and transportation of soil pollutants also impact ecosystems far beyond soils, e.g. aquatic systems, vegetation, insects (links between belowground and aboveground biodiversity: many insects have a life phases below- and aboveground), mammals and other fauna dependent on soil health and biodiversity, pollination, ...The full scope of these impacts is estimated to be extensive, but not comprehensively understood or assessed.

6 Baseline, Indicators/descriptors and quality thresholds/criteria

Connected to the knowledge gaps related to the need for clear definitions, there is a need to set a clear baseline for the assessment of progress towards targets. Currently, knowledge gaps remain on how to set the baseline(s). This while baseline(s) are needed to

define among more policy targets. For example, the baseline could be based on a set of soil descriptors and accompanying criteria. A lack of soil monitoring data regarding required parameters and existing concentrations lies at the base of this knowledge gap. Setting up the baseline at EU level, and assessing different local contexts, is a prerequisite to effectively set targets, implement actions to achieve them, and effective mechanisms to monitor progress towards targets,

Different indicators/descriptors and accompanying quality thresholds/criteria for assessing soil health have been described in scientific literature and applied by policy frameworks (European Environment Agency 2020). Pollution is one of the many aspects which can make a soil unhealthy: a polluted soil is considered an unhealthy soil. However, a lack of understanding and agreement remains on which indicators and criteria to apply to define and assess (the progress towards) healthy soils, levels of soil degradations, and identify soils which need restoration. In order to efficiently set targets, and make progress towards targets, a clear understanding of baselines, indicators and quality thresholds are all key.

3.2.3 Knowledge gaps related to affected/involved stakeholders and their roles

7 Impact of soil pollutants (individual and mixtures, short-term and long-term) on human health

Available research clearly shows that soil pollution poses severe risks to human health. People are throughout their life exposed to soil pollutants through different routes (ingestion, inhalation, skin exposure). The measure of all the exposures throughout a lifetime is referred to as "the exposome". Drinking water contamination, food contamination, transport of pollutants via dust to places frequented by people (paths, playgrounds, houses, gardens, ...), ingestion of soil particles, ... are a few important exposure pathways, how soil pollution can impact human health. In accordance with the knowledge gaps regarding the full impact of soil pollution on soil characteristics, biodiversity and ecosystem functioning, extensive knowledge gaps remain on the impacts of soil pollution on human health. For example, many uncertainties remain on the full impact of diffuse pollutants on human health.

8 Effects (social, economic, cultural) of and on different stakeholders

A variety of different stakeholders are involved in and/or impacted by soil pollution and restoration: citizens, scientists, farmers, industries (e.g. pesticide producers), water companies, policy bodies, ...). For example, soil pollution has a wide impact or possible future impact on stakeholders and land uses which directly or indirectly depend on ecosystem services delivered or supported by healthy soils, such as all citizens, farmers, drinking water producers, cultural heritage (landforms etc.) ... A concrete example are farmers who engage in low-input/nature inclusive/restorative practices, and are confronted with residues from previous practices or transported residues from other fields. Although available information shows clear and extensive impacts of soil pollution on these different stakeholders, the full scope of economic, social and cultural impacts is not fully

understood. Correspondingly, also the potential benefits of soil restoration across different regions have not been fully assessed (e.g. quantification of ecosystem services).

9 Urban Soil Pollution

Urban soil pollution has been documented through several cases, but has been overall poorly studied. Urban soil pollution is associated with specific challenges related to among other issues, t health, water quality (e.g. groundwater pollution) and risks for pollution of surrounding regions. Insights in the full impact of urban soil pollution have been lacking, as well as clear frameworks and initiatives to tackle urban soil pollution.

3.2.4 Knowledge gaps related to solutions and needed conditions (supporting frameworks)

10 Technical/practical tools to prevent agricultural and non-agricultural soil pollution

Although many management practices and technologies, including Integrated Pest Management strategies, agro-ecological and regenerative practices, monitoring systems and precision farming and biocontrol, are available to reduce agricultural soil pollution, it is apparent that significant challenges remain in their uptake. Moreover, further research is still needed to develop and/or optimize these practices for more cropping systems in different climatic and environmental conditions. For example, the use of functional biodiversity in increasing natural pest control and decreasing dependence on pesticides is a highly complex field, which needs specialised adaptation to specific cropping systems and environments. Moreover, adequate risk assessment systems are needed to effectively and efficiently assess new technologies.

11 Technical/practical tools to remediate soil pollution and restore soils

Current available techniques to remediate soil pollution, such as management practices, crop use, the use of microbial technologies, are in need of further research and development to improve remediation effectiveness. Microbial technologies carry great potential, however still need further development regarding increasing efficiency. The process is highly time consuming, which is considered a significant bottleneck in the field of bioremediation.

12 Which policy tools are available to prevent soil pollution, and are they fit-for-purpose?

Different legislations related to soils are implemented at national level. However, there is a strong need to harmonize different legislations which relate to soils. Sometimes different laws conflict, even within the same jurisdiction (e.g. law on soil protection and law on fertilization in the Netherlands). At the same time, important gaps in legislation exist regarding large-scale monitoring and managing of soil pollution, and a EU level policy framework for soils has been absnet. The EU proposal for a Soil Monitoring Law, published in 2023, aims at addressing part of these challenges. However, the proposal is characterized by important gaps regarding e.g. soil biodiversity and soil pollution, namely diffuse pollution. Also clear binding and time bound targets remain absent in the proposal,

as well as a clear link with groundwater and surface water pollution and relevant legislation. Important gaps remain in different policy frameworks with an impact on soil pollution. For example the revised Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD) does not address certain sources of diffuse pollution, such as settlements below 1000 P.E. (population equivalent). Both the existing policy landscape with focus on activities (e.g. agriculture, pesticide use, industrial emissions) should be integrated, as existing legislation regarding management of different resources (e.g. Water Framework Directive, Ambient Air Quality Directives) should be integrated. Important knowledge gaps exist regarding whether or not current legislation and legislation under development will comprehensively address policy needs regarding soil pollution.

13 Socio-economic and market tools to prevent soil pollution/fitness-for-purpose

There is a need for further assessment of available and needed socio-economic and market tools to prevent soil pollution and restore soils. These include incentives and financial support (public and private support), and business models based on soil health, decreasing the soil footprint, remuneration of ecosystem services and stimulating innovation. Public funds need to be directly linked to soil restoration, and not support activities polluting soils. Different market failures contribute to the problem of soil pollution, for example insufficient/heterogeneous internalisation of environmental costs in the EU and beyond, lack of soil data, and a lack of implementation of the polluter pays principle.

14 Which initiatives exist and are needed to involve farmers in soil restoration and prevention of soil pollution?

Different initiatives involving the reduction of soil pollution and enhancement of soil restoration by farmers have been developed, such as projects fostering the implementation of agroecological practices, Integrated Pest Management and organic agriculture. However, a comprehensive overview of all relevant initiatives is needed, as well as, if relevant, information on reasons for discontinuation. This information should contribute to an analysis on which initiatives and supporting conditions would still be needed to increase uptake of good practices throughout Europe.

15 Bottlenecks regarding the implementation and upscaling

Further insight is needed into the bottlenecks and also into enhancing conditions regarding the implementation and upscaling of relevant and valuable techniques to prevent soil pollution and enhance restoration. While many effective techniques to prevent and remediate soil pollution exist, a comprehensive, clear overview on what is preventing their uptake is needed.

16 Modelling

There is a need for further development of modelling tools to assess in an integrative way the impact of soil pollution and the impact of reducing soil pollution and restoring soils on ecosystems and ecosystem services, and associated economic impact.

3.3 Examples of identified research gaps regarding pesticide pollution

Below, examples are given of knowledge gaps already identified during our literature review related to pesticide pollution. Many of these knowledge gaps are also applicable to other sources and types of soil pollution. The below overview will be further developed by the PRTT during the project, to result in a comprehensive overview of the main research gaps across all domains and subdomains of Fig. 1. **This list is hence not final, and consists of a selection of important examples.**

Scope of pesticide pollution

While the minimum number of soil sample points in the EU needed to provide a statistically reliable measurement of soil health has been estimated at 210 000 sampling points, there are currently 34 000 sampling points at Member state level, as well as 41 000 from the LUCAS Soil campaign of 2022, of which 20 000 constitute a repetition of previous LUCAS Soil campaigns. Hence, a large gap of more than 100 000 sampling points exists to assess pollution loads and their fate in the environment. Data from member state level are mostly also not available at EU level. Monitoring schemes are often fragmented, consisting of different sampling methods, frequencies and densities, resulting in a lack of comparability. Also the consistent storing of soil data in an accessible database is lacking. While the LUCAS soil survey provides an overarching monitoring framework, it currently lacks a clear legal mandate, and guaranteed continuity (European Commission 2023a).

Also data on pesticide use are not currently available at EU level, but became mandatory from 2028 through the Regulation on statistics on agricultural inputs and outputs. Pesticides have not been systematically monitored in the EU. Available data originate from the LUCAS Soil survey and from several monitoring and research projects carried out throughout Europe (Silva et al. 2019). Available data show that pesticide mixtures in agricultural soils are the rule rather than the exception. For example, a large monitoring study analysing 317 soil samples, found that 83% of soils contained 1 or more residues, with 58% containing mixtures of pesticide residues, existing of 166 different mixtures (Silva et al. 2019).

Monitoring of pesticide residues in soil has not been mandatory in the EU, and large scale studies on soil pollution by pesticide residues are very limited. Often, they also focus on one pesticide, or a smaller group of compounds. Sampling that has been carried out has often used different sampling strategies and analytics. Hence, an overview of the distribution of pesticides residues across the EU has been missing.

Effects on Biodiversity, Soil Functions and Ecosystem services

In general, current risk assessment doesn't capture cumulative and combined exposure to pesticides, and resulting impacts on soil biodiversity, overall biodiversity and ecosystem functioning (Bopp et al. 2019, Devos et al. 2022, Bopp et al. 2019, Sousa et al. 2022, EEA 2023, van Gestel et al. 2020). Risk assessment also focuses on the active substances of pesticides, and doesn't take into account the full impact of the product (active substance, co-formulants and adjuvants) (Mesnage and Antoniou 2018, SAPEA 2018).

Thresholds for a few pesticide residues have been part of the legislation of a few European countries (Carlou 2007), but mostly for currently banned and highly persistent pesticides (e.g.) DDTs, HCHs, Atrazine, ...). Furthermore, the lack of data on pesticide mixtures in soils, as well as data on the total load of diffuse contamination in soils, have prevented validation and improvement of current risk EU assessment of active substances and pesticides. The latter is currently based on prediction of environmental concentrations, based on recommended application rates. The in-soil indicator organisms used in EU risk assessment only exist in the form of a limited set. Research has pointed to the lack of field data and lack of information on mixture and cumulative effects on soil organisms, including non-standard and native species and communities, soil functioning and ecosystem services (Geissen et al. 2021).

Although some studies have carried out economical assessments of the impact of agriculture on the environment, the environmental externalities of pesticide pollution haven't been fully assessed across Europe. Likewise, benefits of decreasing soil pollution and positive impacts of restoring soil health on biodiversity and ecosystem services, including long-term, sustainable production of food, haven't been comprehensively included in current evaluation assessments, including in existing models. For example, models assessing the impact of reducing pesticides often don't consider the medium and long term positive impacts regarding crop production which could result from soil restoration and enhancement of ecosystem services, such as increased pollination, natural pest control and protection against erosion.

Effects on human health

Analogous to the research gaps regarding the assessment of the impact of pesticides on the environment, the complete impact of total pesticide exposure through all exposure routes, taking into account complete products, mixture and cumulative effects, for human health remains currently unclear. For example, current risk assessment focuses mostly on pesticide exposure through food ingestion, while experts point out that exposure via air and skin are main routes of exposure, which are probably currently not adequately assessed. Research projects show widespread pesticide contamination in soils, air, waterways, indoor dust, animals and humans. However, systematic monitoring data of pesticide residues in humans and indoor dust are not available. A large body of research shows the links between pesticide exposure and a variety of health impacts. Certain illnesses, such as Parkinson's disease, have been listed as occupational diseases in France, due to their high prevalence among farmers and farmworkers (Shan et al. 2023, Bloem and Boonstra 2023). A comprehensive assessment covering toxicity effects of pesticide mixtures and cumulative effects, spatial analysis of pesticide exposure and prevalence of specific health impacts in Europe is needed to assess these impacts further.

Examples of Impact on and of Stakeholders

Many uncertainties remain on how and if policies underway will be fit for purpose to reach goals set by the Green Deal and the Soil Mission, and how they will be interlinked. Objectives of the Green Deal include the reduction of chemical pesticides by 50%, the

reduction of artificial fertilisers by 20% and the increase of organic agriculture of 25% by 2030. However, proposals for key legislation, part of the Green Deal, and needed to fulfill the Green Deal objectives, have been withdrawn, such as the SUR proposal in February 2024, or delayed, such as the Framework for Sustainable Food Systems. Therefore, it is unclear when and how the Green Deal objectives will be met. Furthermore, linkages between policies under development and current legislation, such as the Common Agricultural Policy, are uncertain. These linkages, as well as effective result-based implementation of legislation, are deemed essential to reach soil related goals. Current and past legislation have been frequently not adequately implemented. An important research question is hence how to ensure consistency and needed linkages between different policies, and how to ensure effective, result-based implementation of legislation, as well as monitoring of the results of policy measurements and application of feedback mechanisms.

Many projects and initiatives throughout Europe have focused on gathering and exchanging insights and knowledge regarding from and between farmers, between farmers, research and policy. Projects focusing on lighthouse farms, practical demonstrations and cooperation and knowledge exchange across groups of farms have been identified as valuable and effective. However, a recurring bottleneck is the lack of continuity of projects, and the lack of further, large-scale implementation of land management techniques, such as IPM/ICM, which have been found successful. An important identified research question is hence how to create optimal overarching frameworks to successfully implement successful agricultural management practices based on prevention and enhancement of ecosystem services, including healthy soil functioning, at a large scale.

Solutions to soil pollution

Preventative measures

Successful examples of preventative, low-input and nature-inclusive agricultural practices have been applied throughout Europe. Integrated Pest Management (IPM), which is based on preventative measures, increasing natural pest control (beneficial organisms) and the resilience of cropping systems against pests, while only using chemical pesticides when all other methods have been exhausted and failed, is mandatory in the EU since 2014, through the sustainable use of pesticides directive (dir. (EC) 128/2009, SUD). Multiple analyses of EU bodies have pointed to the lack of implementation of IPM since then. The proposal for a Sustainable Use of Pesticides Regulation (European Commission 2022a), which will replace the current directive, was published by the European Commission as an answer to the lack of pesticide reductions and implementation of IPM since 2009.

A wide variety of examples of IPM practices is available for diverse cropping systems throughout Europe. The European Commission recently published a database of 1300 examples of practices, techniques and technologies for IPM, including 273 crop-specific guidelines, accompanied by a study assessing their effectiveness (European Commission 2023b). However, the supporting framework to implement practices, such as independent advisory systems, and hence access of farmers to alternative management techniques,

has been lacking in most member states. On the other hand, more research is needed to further develop and optimise IPM practices for all cropping systems and environmental conditions.

In general, pesticide use is heavily subjected to 'locked-in' mechanisms regarding agronomy and research, economics, knowledge and policy, which have prevented reducing pesticides. These locked-in mechanisms, and barriers to overcome them, have been identified by the ongoing Sprint project

A lock-in mechanism consists of the fact that policy, funding and infrastructure mechanisms are focused on supporting a limited set of farming models and major crops. For example, current agricultural legislation and funding doesn't secure linkages between funding and protection of the environment and enhancement of ecosystem services (OECD 2023).

Important examples of research topics to include in the roadmap are hence:

- How to overcome lack of implementation of current policies and increase accessibility and wide-scale implementation of existing alternatives
- How to secure linkage and coherence between policies, advisory systems, funding/tax mechanisms, value chains and ecosystem services.
- How to further optimize agricultural management practices based on preventative measures, covering existing cropping systems and environmental conditions throughout Europe.

Engagement within the Think Tanks

Science-policy-practice interface is a hot topic of scientific research (Miles et al. 2017) and especially relevant to environmental issues (Cvitanovic and Hobday 2018) within the context of the circular economy and sustainability (Kujala et al. 2023, Heikkinen et al. 2023). One of the primary benefits of stakeholder engagement (Kovács et al. 2021) is the creation of links between science and society, providing access to additional information or resources, and improving the relevance or utility of the research to users and beneficiaries. Concretely, through engagement, the project's results can be tailored to local contexts, increase the possibility that the outcomes are applied, and therefore, have a positive impact. We strongly believe that this will encourage and enhance the commitment of said stakeholders during the implementation of this project.

Identification of the stakeholders

Identification of stakeholders was a process partly linked to the conceptual framework. While the General Agreement of the SOLO project (GA) set the main categories (policymakers, civil society, practitioners, industry agents, scientists) of stakeholders to be approached, the conceptual framework served as an additional aspect of consideration.

Thus, it was important to find stakeholders for all of the stakeholder categories of the conceptual framework reflecting

- on how the impact of pollution affects them (negatively or positively) and
- on what kind of relationship they have with decision making (influencing and making/taking decisions).

Sectors (agro and non-agro), regional representation and decision making levels (EU, regional, national, local) were considered. PRTT's choices of stakeholders promotes science-policy-practice interface by having stakeholders from science, policy and practice. The stakeholder involvement process resulted in a good representation both regarding geographic origin and professional background. Most of our, in total 21, stakeholders fit into more than one professional category. When organisational affiliation is not playing a role the numbers of scientists change. The figure on sectors is a good indication of the intertwined nature of sectors. Fig. 3 below is a demonstration of it.

Figure 3. [doi](#)

Introduction of stakeholders by different categories.

For the GA categories mainly organisational affiliation was applied to distinguish between the stakeholders:

Policy maker: member of policy making bodies and public institutions with the task of preparing/developing/implementing/reviewing policy

Civil society: NGOs, giving voice to the citizens

Practitioners: farmers, advisors without organisational affiliation

Business: business organisations and business interest groups

Scientists: Scientists (including PhD students) having affiliation to academic (education and/or research) institutions.

For the science-policy-practice interface:

Science: all scientists irrespective of organisational affiliation

Policy: non-scientists policy makers

Practice: all non-scientists other than policy makers

Stakeholder engagement process

Stakeholders have been engaged from the very early stage of development of the scoping document. Most of the stakeholders had been individually approached and the project explained to them. Their reflections had influenced the first draft of the document, particularly the system-approach of Figure 1. The first draft of the scoping document was sent to all stakeholders, and based on their availability they reflected on the content during semi-structured interviews, or just shared their opinion in oral or written form. Stakeholders' comments were integrated into the current version. Fig. 4 depicts this process

Figure 4. [doi](#)
Stakeholder involvement.

Stakeholders expressed their views on the presentation of the content and also on the issues addressed in the document as a whole and particularly in the figures, and tables. Stakeholders' opinions were summarised based on the content of their feedback into two main categories: Format (F) (e.g.: transparency of the figures and tables), and Substance (S), and the category of Substance was broken down into three subcategories depending on what action it required: to add (Sa), to complete (Sc), to improve understanding (Siu). The scoping document was modified after assessment and evaluation of the comments. All comments were relevant and useful. The format of the figure has been changed, and some of the suggestions were integrated into the document. However, not all of the comments were directly inserted, in some cases further elaboration of the topic was sufficient.

Table 2 summarises the comments on the first drafts and their acceptance by the main categories of the stakeholders

Table 2.

Examples of Stakeholder's reflections on the first draft.

Stakeholder by categories	overall feedback	categories of specific comments	Uptake (X) (or otherwise explain)
Scientist	positive	Sa, Siu	...
Practice	positive	F, Sc, Siu	
Civil society	positive	Sa, Sc	
Policy	positive	Sa, Sc, Siu	
Business	positive	Sa, Sc,	
...			

Appendix

The relationship between the EU Soil Monitoring Law proposal and the Figure 1 in the scoping document.

Monitoring requirements of SML are set in the Annexes of the SML proposal. Table 3 below shows the links between Fig. 1 of this scoping document and the Annexes of the SML.

Table 3.

Table 1 of Appendix I Links between Figure 1 and Annexes of SML.

Figure 1	Annexes of SML
1) Soil pollution	Annex I Soil Descriptors, Criteria for Healthy Soil Condition, and Land Take and Soil Sealing Indicators
2) Effects of pollution	Annex II Methodologies Annex VI Phases and Requirements of Site-specific Risk Assessment Annex VII Content of Register of Potentially Contaminated Sites and Contaminated Sites
3) Stakeholders having impact on pollution or being impacted by pollution	Annex IV Programmes, Plans, Targets and Measures referred to in Article 10
4) Solutions to mitigate Soil Pollution	Annex III. Sustainable Soil Management Principles Annex V Indicative List of Risk Reduction Measures, Annex VI Phases and Requirements of Site-specific Risk Assessment

Table 4 shows which part of Annex I (Soil Descriptors, Criteria for Healthy Soil Condition, and Land Take and Soil Sealing Indicators) of the Soil Monitoring Law proposal is relevant to PRTT. Annex I makes links between soil degradation, soil descriptors, soil health criteria and who sets the criteria: Part A – by the EU, Part B – by the member states, Part C – without criteria.

Table 4.

Table 2 of Appendix I shows which part of Annex I (Soil Descriptors, Criteria for Healthy Soil Condition, and Land Take and Soil Sealing Indicators) is relevant to PRTT. (Annex I makes links between soil degradation, soil descriptors, soil health criteria and who sets the criteria: Part A – by the EU, Part B – by the member states, Part C – without criteria).

Aspect of soil degradation	Soil descriptor	Criteria for healthy soil condition	Land areas that shall be excluded from achieving the related criterion
Part A: soil descriptors with criteria for healthy soil condition established at Union level			
Salinization	Electrical Conductivity (deci-Siemens per meter)	< 4 dS m ⁻¹ when using saturated soil paste extract (eEC) measurement method, or equivalent criterion if using another measurement method	Naturally saline land areas; Land areas directly affected by sea level rise
Part B: soil descriptors with criteria for healthy soil condition established at Member States level			
Excess nutrient content in soil	Extractable phosphorus (mg per kg)	< "maximum value"; The "maximum value" shall be laid down by the Member State within the range 30-50 mg kg ⁻¹	No exclusion
Soil contamination	- concentration of heavy metals in soil: As, Sb, Cd, Co, Cr (total), Cr (VI), Cu, Hg, Pb, Ni, Tl, V, Zn (µg per kg)	Reasonable assurance, obtained from soil point sampling, identification and investigation of contaminated sites and any other relevant information, that no unacceptable risk for human health and the environment from soil contamination exists.	No exclusion
	- concentration of a selection of organic contaminants established by Member States and taking into account existing concentration limits e.g. for water quality and air emissions in Union legislation	Habitats with naturally high concentration of heavy metals that are included in Annex I of Council Directive 92/43/EEC3 shall remain protected.	
Part C: soil descriptors without criteria			
Excess nutrient content in soil		Nitrogen in soil (mg g ⁻¹)	
Acidification		Soil acidity (pH)	
Loss of soil biodiversity		Soil basal respiration ((mm3 O2 g ⁻¹ hr ⁻¹) in dry soil	

Aspect of soil degradation	Soil descriptor	Criteria for healthy soil condition	Land areas that shall be excluded from achieving the related criterion
			<p>Member States may also select other optional soil descriptors for biodiversity such as: - metabarcoding of bacteria, fungi, protists and animals; - abundance and diversity of nematodes; - microbial biomass; - abundance and diversity of earthworms (in cropland);</p> <p>- invasive alien species and plant pests</p>

References

- Adhikari K, Hartemink A (2016) Linking soils to ecosystem services — A global review. *Geoderma* 262: 101-111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2015.08.009>
- Anthony M, Bender SF, van der Heijden MA (2023) Enumerating soil biodiversity. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 120 (33). <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2304663120>
- Antikainen R, Haapanen R, Lemola R, Nousiainen J, Rekolainen S (2008) Nitrogen and Phosphorus Flows in the Finnish Agricultural and Forest Sectors, 1910–2000. *Water, Air, and Soil Pollution* 194: 163-177. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11270-008-9705-0>
- Aparicio JD, Raimondo EE, Saez JM, Costa-Gutierrez SB, Álvarez A, Benimeli CS, Polti MA (2022) The current approach to soil remediation: A review of physicochemical and biological technologies, and the potential of their strategic combination. *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering* 10 (2). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2022.107141>
- Babí Almenar J, Elliot T, Rugani B, Philippe B, Navarrete Gutierrez T, Sonnemann G, Geneletti D (2021) Nexus between nature-based solutions, ecosystem services and urban challenges. *Land Use Policy* 100 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2020.104898>
- Baensch-Baltruschat B, Kocher B, Kochleus C, Stock F, Reifferscheid G (2021) Tyre and road wear particles - A calculation of generation, transport and release to water and soil with special regard to German roads. *Science of The Total Environment* 752 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.141939>
- Ballabio C, Panagos P, Lugato E, Huang J, Orgiazzi A, Jones A, Fernández-Ugalde O, Borrelli P, Montanarella L (2018) Copper distribution in European topsoils: An assessment based on LUCAS soil survey. *Science of The Total Environment* 636: 282-298. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.04.268>
- Ballabio C, Jiskra M, Osterwalder S, Borrelli P, Montanarella L, Panagos P (2021) A spatial assessment of mercury content in the European Union topsoil. *Science of The Total Environment* 769 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.144755>
- Bloem BR, Boonstra TA (2023) The inadequacy of current pesticide regulations for protecting brain health: the case of glyphosate and Parkinson's disease. *The Lancet Planetary Health* 7 (12). [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2542-5196\(23\)00255-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2542-5196(23)00255-3)

- Bopp S, Kienzler A, Richarz A, van der Linden S, Pains A, Parissis N, Worth A (2019) Regulatory assessment and risk management of chemical mixtures: challenges and ways forward. *Critical Reviews in Toxicology* 49 (2): 174-189. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408444.2019.1579169>
- Bouma J (2014) Soil science contributions towards Sustainable Development Goals and their implementation: linking soil functions with ecosystem services. *Journal of Plant Nutrition and Soil Science* 177 (2): 111-120. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jpln.201300646>
- Brühl C, Zaller J (2021) Indirect herbicide effects on biodiversity, ecosystem functions, and interactions with global changes. *Herbicides* 231-272. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-823674-1.00005-5>
- Carlon C (2007) Derivation methods of soil screening values in Europe. A review and evaluation of national procedures towards harmonisation. https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ESDB_Archive/eusoils_docs/other/EUR22805.pdf
- Chiaia-Hernandez A, Keller A, Wächter D, Steinlin C, Camenzuli L, Hollender J, Kruss M (2017) Long-Term Persistence of Pesticides and TPs in Archived Agricultural Soil Samples and Comparison with Pesticide Application. *Environmental Science & Technology* 51 (18): 10642-10651. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.7b02529>
- Council of the European Union (2019) Towards a Sustainable Chemicals Policy Strategy of the Union - Council conclusions. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/40042/st10713-en19.pdf>
- Covaci A, Geens T, Roosens L, Ali N, Van den Eede N, Ionaș A, Malarvannan G, Dirtu A (2011) Human Exposure and Health Risks to Emerging Organic Contaminants. *The Handbook of Environmental Chemistry* 243-305. https://doi.org/10.1007/698_2011_126
- Cox K, Covernton G, Davies H, Dower J, Juanes F, Dudas S (2019) Human Consumption of Microplastics. *Environmental Science & Technology* 53 (12): 7068-7074. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.9b01517>
- Cvitanovic C, Hobday A (2018) Building optimism at the environmental science-policy-practice interface through the study of bright spots. *Nature Communications* 9 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-05977-w>
- Cycoń M, Mroziak A, Piotrowska-Seget Z (2019) Antibiotics in the Soil Environment—Degradation and Their Impact on Microbial Activity and Diversity. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 10 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2019.00338>
- Devos Y, Arena M, Ashe S, Blanck M, Bray E, Broglia A, Bronzwaer S, Cafaro A, Corsini E, Dujardin B, Dumont AF, Garcia MG, Gardi C, Guerra B, Kass GN, Maggiore A, Martino L, Merten C, Percivaldi C, Szoradi A, Martinez SV, Ververis E, Vrbos D, Hugas M (2022) Addressing the need for safe, nutritious and sustainable food: Outcomes of the “ONE – Health, Environment & Society – Conference 2022”. *Trends in Food Science & Technology* 129: 164-178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2022.09.014>
- De Vries W, Römkens PF, Kros J, Voogd JC, Schulte-Uebbing LF (2022) Impacts of nutrients and heavy metals in European agriculture. Current and critical inputs in relation to air, soil and water quality.
- Dushkova D, Haase A, Wolff M, Haase D (2021) Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) in Cities and Their Interactions with Urban Land, Ecosystems, Built Environments and People: Debating Societal Implications. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7248520>

- EEA (2022) Progress in the management of contaminated sites in Europe <https://www.eea.europa.eu/ims/progress-inthe-management-of>. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/ims/progress-inthe-management-of>
- EEA (2023) How pesticides impact human health and ecosystems in Europe. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/how-pesticides-impact-human-health>
- EEB (2023) Assessment of the European Commission proposal for a Soil Monitoring Law. <https://eeb.org/library/assessment-of-the-european-commission-proposal-for-a-soil-monitoring-law/>
- EIP AGRI (2020) Reducing the plastic footprint of agriculture. https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/sites/default/files/eip-agri_fg41_plastic_footprint_starting_paper_2020_en.pdf
- EurEau (2023) EurEau reaction to the Commission's Soil Monitoring Law. <https://www.eureau.org/news/794-eureau-reaction-to-the-commission-s-soil-monitoring-law>
- European Commission (2011) Technical support on POP regulation. https://ec.europa.eu/environment/chemicals/international_conventions/pdf/syntesis_report2.pdf
- European Commission (2019) Environmental and Health Risks of Microplastic Pollution. https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/sites/default/files/eip-agri_fg41_plastic_footprint_starting_paper_2020_en.pdf
- European Commission (2020a) Commission communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability Towards a Toxic-free Environment COM/2020/667 final. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2020%3A667%3AFIN>
- European Commission (2020b) Report on the SUD. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/eeacebd-9a94-11ea-9d2d-01aa75ed71a1>
- European Commission, Veerman C, Pinto Correia T, Bastioli Cea, et al. (2020) European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Caring for soil is caring for life – Ensure 75% of soils are healthy by 2030 for healthy food, people, nature and climate – Interim report of the mission board for soil health and food, Publications Office, 2020, . <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/918775>
- European Commission (2021a) COMMISSION [Zero Pollution Action Plan – Towards zero pollution for air, water and soil](https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/zero-pollution-action-plan_en) - 2019-2023. https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/zero-pollution-action-plan_en
- European Commission (2021b) Commission Internal Working Document - European Missions – [A Soil Deal for Europe, 100 living labhouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030. Implementation Plan. 77p.](https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-09/soil_mission_implementation_plan_final_for_publication.pdf) https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-09/soil_mission_implementation_plan_final_for_publication.pdf
- European Commission (2021c) Ensuring that polluters pay - Austria. https://environment.ec.europa.eu/document/download/b2a2c5ea-1217-4c01-9ffb-e6cda87e0bc8_en?filename=Austria.pdf. Accessed on: 2024-2-01.
- European Commission (2022a) COMMISSION [Proposal for a Regulation on the sustainable use of plant protection products and amending Regulation \(EU\) 2021/2115 – Proposal, Annex and Impact Assessment.](https://food.ec.europa.eu/plants/pesticides/sustainable-use-pesticides_en) https://food.ec.europa.eu/plants/pesticides/sustainable-use-pesticides_en
- European Commission (2022b) Regulation (EU) 2022/2379 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 November 2022 on statistics on agricultural input and output,

amending Commission Regulation (EC) No 617/2008 and repealing Regulations (EC) No 1165/2008, (EC) No 543/2009 and (EC) No 1185/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council and Council Directive 96/16/EC (Text with EEA relevance). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/2379/oj>

- European Commission (2023a) Commission [Proposal for a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience – Proposal, Annex and Impact Assessment](https://environment.ec.europa.eu/publications/proposal-directive-soil-monitoring-and-resilience_en). https://environment.ec.europa.eu/publications/proposal-directive-soil-monitoring-and-resilience_en
- European Commission (2023b) Using less chemical pesticides: European Commission publishes toolbox of good practices. https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/news/using-less-chemical-pesticides-european-commission-publishes-toolbox-good-practices-2023-02-28_en
- European Court of Auditors (2020) Report on the SUD. <https://www.eca.europa.eu/en/publications?did=53001>
- European Environment Agency (2018) Agriculture: nitrogen balance. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/airs/2018/natural-capital/agricultural-land-nitrogen-balance>
- European Environment Agency (2019) The European environment— state and outlook 2020. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/soer/2020>
- European Environment Agency (2020) Report: [Soil monitoring in Europe — Indicators and thresholds for soil health assessments](https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/soil-monitoring-in-europe). <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/soil-monitoring-in-europe>
- European Environmental Bureau (2024) European Parliament vote places soil health on shaky ground. <https://eeb.org/european-parliament-vote-places-soil-health-on-shaky-ground/>. Accessed on: 2024-4-19.
- European Medicines Agency (2021) Sales of veterinary antimicrobial agents in 31 European countries in 2019 and 2020. https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/report/sales-veterinary-antimicrobial-agents-31-european-countries-2019-2020-trends2010-2020-eleventh_en.pdf
- European Parliamentary Research Service (2018) Implementation assessment on SUD. [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2018/627113/EPRS_STU\(2018\)627113_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2018/627113/EPRS_STU(2018)627113_EN.pdf)
- Eurostat (2022a) Pesticide Sales. online data code: aei_fm_salpest09. Utilised agricultural area data from EUROSTAT (2022) Utilised agricultural area by categories. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00025/default/table?lang=en>
- Eurostat (2022b) Generation of waste by waste category, hazardousness and NACE Rev. 2 activity.
- FAO (2020) Towards a definition of soil health, ITPS Intergovernmental technical panel on Soils Soil Letters #1.
- Frelih-Larsen A, Sprint project, et al. (2022) Pesticide lock-in and barriers to transition towards sustainable plant protection. <https://sprint-h2020.eu/index.php/doclink/d7-1-final/eyJ0eXAiOiJKV1QiLCJhbGciOiJIUzI1NiJ9.eyJzdWIiOiJkNy0xLWZpbmFslwiiaWF0IjoxNjg3NTMyMDQEW5kbhXw>
- Geissen V, Silva V, Lwanga EH, Beriot N, Oostindie K, Bin Z, Pyne E, Busink S, Zomer P, Mol H, Ritsema C (2021) Cocktails of pesticide residues in conventional and organic farming systems in Europe – Legacy of the past and turning point for the future. *Environmental Pollution* 278 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2021.116827>

- GIZ (2021) Ecosystem Soil - Bringing nature-based solutions on climate change and biodiversity conservation down to earth. https://www.gesunde-erde.net/media/giz_eba_ecosystem-soil_final.pdf
- Greiner L, Keller A, Grêt-Regamey A, Papritz A (2017) Soil function assessment: review of methods for quantifying the contributions of soils to ecosystem services. *Land Use Policy* 69: 224-237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2017.06.025>
- Grifoni M, Franchi E, Fusini D, Vocciante M, Barbafieri M, Pedron F, Rosellini I, Petruzzelli G (2022) Soil Remediation: Towards a Resilient and Adaptive Approach to Deal with the Ever-Changing Environmental Challenges. *Environments* 9 (2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/environments9020018>
- Gros M, Mas-Pla J, Boy-Roura M, Geli I, Domingo F, Petrović M (2019) Veterinary pharmaceuticals and antibiotics in manure and slurry and their fate in amended agricultural soils: Findings from an experimental field site (Baix Empordà, NE Catalonia). *Science of The Total Environment* 654: 1337-1349. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.11.061>
- Gunstone T, Cornelisse T, Klein K, Dubey A, Donley N (2021) Pesticides and Soil Invertebrates: A Hazard Assessment. *Frontiers in Environmental Science* 9 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2021.643847>
- Gworek B, Kijewska M, Wrzosek J, Graniewska M (2021) Pharmaceuticals in the Soil and Plant Environment: a Review. *Water, Air, & Soil Pollution* 232 (4). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11270-020-04954-8>
- Heikkinen A, Kujala J, Blomberg A (2023) Outlining Stakeholder Engagement in a Sustainable Circular Economy. *Stakeholder Engagement in a Sustainable Circular Economy* 1-15. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-31937-2_1
- Huysegoms L, Cappuyns V (2017) Critical review of decision support tools for sustainability assessment of site remediation options. *Journal of Environmental Management* 196: 278-296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2017.03.002>
- Hvězdová M, Kosubová P, Košíková M, Scherr K, Šimek Z, Brodský L, Šudoma M, Škulcová L, Sářka M, Svobodová M, Krkošková L, Vašíčková J, Neuwirthová N, Bielská L, Hofman J (2018) Currently and recently used pesticides in Central European arable soils. *Science of The Total Environment* 361-370. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.09.049>
- Institute of Environmental Sciences (CML), Leiden University, Royal HaskoningDHV (2024) Atlas bestrijdingsmiddelen in oppervlaktewater. <https://www.bestrijdingsmiddelenatlas.nl/atlas/1/1>. Accessed on: 2024-3-08.
- IPM Works (2022) An EU-wide farm network demonstrating and promoting cost-effective IPM strategies. <https://ipmworks.net/>
- IUNG (2019) The impact of soil degradation on human health. Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation (IUNG). <https://www.deltares.nl/app/uploads/2019/02/Deliverable1.7-Report-5-FINAL-DEF.pdf>
- Jónsson J, Davíðsdóttir B (2016) Classification and valuation of soil ecosystem services. *Agricultural Systems* 145: 24-38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2016.02.010>
- JRC, Maes J, et al. (2020) Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystems and their Services: An EU ecosystem assessment. <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC120383>
- Klátyik S, Simon G, Oláh M, Mesnage R, Antoniou M, Zaller J, Székács A (2023) Terrestrial ecotoxicity of glyphosate, its formulations, and co-formulants: evidence from

- 2010–2023. *Environmental Sciences Europe* 35 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-023-00758-9>
- Kovács E, Mile O, Fabók V, Margóczy K, Kalóczkai Á, Kasza V, Nagyné Grecs A, Bankovics A, Mihók B (2021) Fostering adaptive co-management with stakeholder participation in the surroundings of soda pans in Kiskunság, Hungary – An assessment. *Land Use Policy* 100 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2020.104894>
 - Kujala J, Heikkinen A, Blomberg A (2023) Stakeholder Engagement in a Sustainable Circular Economy. Palgrave Macmillan Cham ISBN: 978-3-031-31937-2 <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-31937-2>
 - Lacalle RG, Becerril JM, Garbisu C (2020) Biological Methods of Polluted Soil Remediation for an Effective Economically-Optimal Recovery of Soil Health and Ecosystem Services. *Journal of Environmental Science and Public Health* 04 (02). <https://doi.org/10.26502/jesph.96120089>
 - Lim X (2021) Microplastics are everywhere — but are they harmful? *Nature* 593 (7857): 22-25. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-021-01143-3>
 - Lofty J, Muhawenimana V, Wilson CA, Ouro P (2022) Microplastics removal from a primary settler tank in a wastewater treatment plant and estimations of contamination onto European agricultural land via sewage sludge recycling. *Environmental Pollution* 304 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2022.119198>
 - Mandl K, Cantelmo C, Gruber E, Faber F, Friedrich B, Zaller J (2018) Effects of Glyphosate-, Glufosinate- and Flazasulfuron-Based Herbicides on Soil Microorganisms in a Vineyard. *Bulletin of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology* 101 (5): 562-569. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00128-018-2438-x>
 - Matsuzaki R, Gunnigle E, Geissen V, Clarke G, Nagpal J, Cryan JF (2023) Pesticide exposure and the microbiota-gut-brain axis. *The ISME Journal* 17 (8): 1153-1166. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41396-023-01450-9>
 - Mesnage R, Antoniou M (2018) Ignoring Adjuvant Toxicity Falsifies the Safety Profile of Commercial Pesticides. *Frontiers in Public Health* 5 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2017.00361>
 - Miles A, DeLonge M, Carlisle L (2017) Triggering a positive research and policy feedback cycle to support a transition to agroecology and sustainable food systems. *Agroecology and Sustainable Food Systems* 41 (7): 855-879. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21683565.2017.1331179>
 - Ministry of the Environment, Finland (2007) Government Decree on the Assessment of Soil Contamination and Remediation Needs (2007), (214/2007, March 1, 2007) 63.
 - Montanarella L, Panagos P (2021) The relevance of sustainable soil management within the European Green Deal. *Land Use Policy* 100 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2020.104950>
 - Morgado R, Loureiro S, González-Alcaraz M (2018) Changes in Soil Ecosystem Structure and Functions Due to Soil Contamination. *Soil Pollution* 59-87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-849873-6.00003-0>
 - Mulligan CN, Yong RN, Gibbs BF (2001) Remediation technologies for metal-contaminated soils and groundwater: an evaluation. *Engineering Geology* 60: 193-207. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0013-7952\(00\)00101-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0013-7952(00)00101-0)
 - Navarro I, de la Torre A, Sanz P, Baldi I, Harkes P, Huerta-Lwanga E, Nørgaard T, Glavan M, Pasković I, Pasković MP, Abrantes N, Campos I, Alcon F, Contreras J, Alaoui A, Hofman J, Vested A, Bureau M, Aparicio V, Mandrioli D, Sgargi D, Mol H, Geissen V,

- Silva V, Martínez MÁ (2023) Occurrence of pesticide residues in indoor dust of farmworker households across Europe and Argentina. *Science of The Total Environment* 905 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.167797>
- Nielsen HØ, Konrad MTH, Pedersen AB, Gyldenkærne S (2023) Ex-post evaluation of the Danish pesticide tax: A novel and effective tax design. *Land Use Policy* 126 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2023.106549>
 - OECD (2023) *Agricultural Policy Monitoring and Evaluation 2023: Adapting Agriculture to Climate Change*. <https://doi.org/10.1787/b14de474-en>
 - Orgiazzi A, Panagos P, Fernández-Ugalde O, Wojda P, Labouyrie M, Ballabio C, Franco A, Pistocchi A, Montanarella L, Jones A (2022) LUCAS Soil Biodiversity and LUCAS Soil Pesticides, new tools for research and policy development. *European Journal of Soil Science* 73 (5). <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13299>
 - Orgiazzi A (2016) *Global Soil Biodiversity Atlas*. European Commission.
 - O'Riordan R, et al. (2021) The Ecosystem services of urban soils: A review. *Geoderma* 395 (3): 115076. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2021.115076>
 - Orton TG, Saby NP, Arrouays D, Jolivet CC, Villanneau EJ, Marchant BP, Caria G, Barriuso E, Bispo A, Briand O (2013) Spatial distribution of Lindane concentration in topsoil across France. *Science of The Total Environment* 443: 338-350. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2012.10.103>
 - Panagos P, Jiskra M, Borrelli P, Liakos L, Ballabio C (2021) Mercury in European topsoils: Anthropogenic sources, stocks and fluxes. *Environmental Research* 201 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2021.111556>
 - Panagos P, Köningner J, Ballabio C, Liakos L, Muntwyler A, Borrelli P, Lugato E (2022) Improving the phosphorus budget of European agricultural soils. *Science of The Total Environment* 853 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.158706>
 - Paya Perez A, E.N. R (2018) Status of local soil contamination in Europe: Revision of the indicator “Progress in the management contaminated sites in Europe. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg. <https://doi.org/10.2760/093804>
 - Ponge J (2015) The soil as an ecosystem. *Biology and Fertility of Soils* 51 (6): 645-648. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00374-015-1016-1>
 - Pose-Juan E, Sánchez-Martín M, Andrades MS, Rodríguez-Cruz MS, Herrero-Hernández E (2015) Pesticide residues in vineyard soils from Spain: Spatial and temporal distributions. *Science of The Total Environment* 514: 351-358. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.01.076>
 - Pourret O, Hursthouse A (2019) It's Time to Replace the Term “Heavy Metals” with “Potentially Toxic Elements” When Reporting Environmental Research. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 16 (22). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16224446>
 - Pulleman M, Creamer R, Hamer U, Helder J, Pelosi C, Pérès G, Rutgers M (2012) Soil biodiversity, biological indicators and soil ecosystem services—an overview of European approaches. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability* 4 (5): 529-538. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2012.10.009>
 - Qu C, Albanese S, Chen W, Lima A, Doherty A, Piccolo A, Arienzo M, Qi S, De Vivo B (2016) The status of organochlorine pesticide contamination in the soils of the Campanian Plain, southern Italy, and correlations with soil properties and cancer risk. *Environmental Pollution* 216: 500-511. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2016.05.089>

- Rigal S, Dakos V, Alonso H, Auniņš A, Benkő Z, Brotons L, Chodkiewicz T, Chylarecki P, de Carli E, Del Moral JC, Domşa C, Escandell V, Fontaine B, Foppen R, Gregory R, Harris S, Herrando S, Husby M, Ieronymidou C, Jiguet F, Kennedy J, Klvaňová A, Kmecl P, Kuczyński L, Kurlavičius P, Kálás JA, Lehtikoinen A, Lindström Å, Lorrillièr R, Moshøj C, Nellis R, Noble D, Eskildsen DP, Paquet J, Pélissié M, Pladevall C, Portolou D, Reif J, Schmid H, Seaman B, Szabo ZD, Szép T, Florenzano GT, Teufelbauer N, Trautmann S, van Turnhout C, Vermouzek Z, Vikstrøm T, Voříšek P, Weiserbs A, Devictor V (2023) Farmland practices are driving bird population decline across Europe. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 120 (21): e2216573120. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2216573120>
- Rockström J, Gupta J, Qin D, Lade S, Abrams J, Andersen L, Armstrong McKay D, Bai X, Bala G, Bunn S, Ciobanu D, DeClerck F, Ebi K, Gifford L, Gordon C, Hasan S, Kanie N, Lenton T, Loriani S, Liverman D, Mohamed A, Nakicenovic N, Obura D, Ospina D, Prodani K, Rammelt C, Sakschewski B, Scholtens J, Stewart-Koster B, Tharammal T, van Vuuren D, Verburg P, Winkelmann R, Zimm C, Bennett E, Bringezu S, Broadgate W, Green P, Huang L, Jacobson L, Ndehedehe C, Pedde S, Rocha J, Scheffer M, Schulte-Uebbing L, de Vries W, Xiao C, Xu C, Xu X, Zafra-Calvo N, Zhang X (2023) Safe and just Earth system boundaries. *Nature* 619 (7968): 102-111. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06083-8>
- Rodríguez-Eugenio N, McLaughlin M, Pennock D, FAO (2018) Soil Pollution: a hidden reality. URL: <https://www.fao.org/3/I9183EN/i9183en.pdf>
- Roslund M, Laitinen O, Sinkkonen A (2024) Scoping review on soil microbiome and gut health—Are soil microorganisms missing from the planetary health plate? *People and Nature* <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.10638>
- Ruuskanen S, Fuchs B, Nissinen R, Puigbò P, Rainio M, Saikkonen K, Helander M (2023) Ecosystem consequences of herbicides: the role of microbiome. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 38 (1): 35-43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2022.09.009>
- SAPEA (2018) Improving authorisation processes for plant protection products in Europe: a scientific perspective on the potential risks to human health, Evidence Review Report No 3, Science Advice for Policy by European Academies, Berlin. <https://doi.org/10.26356/plantprotectionproducts>
- Shan L, Heusinkveld H, Paul K, Hughes S, Darweesh SL, Bloem B, Homberg J (2023) Towards improved screening of toxins for Parkinson's risk. *npj Parkinson's Disease* 9 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41531-023-00615-9>
- Silva V, Mol HJ, Zomer P, Tienstra M, Ritsema C, Geissen V (2019) Pesticide residues in European agricultural soils – A hidden reality unfolded. *Science of The Total Environment* 653: 1532-1545. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.10.441>
- Silva V, Yang X, Fleskens L, Ritsema C, Geissen V (2022) Environmental and human health at risk – Scenarios to achieve the Farm to Fork 50% pesticide reduction goals. *Environment International* 165 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2022.107296>
- Silva V, Gai L, Harkes P, Tan G, Ritsema C, Alcon F, Contreras J, Abrantes N, Campos I, Baldi I, Bureau M, Christ F, Mandrioli D, Sgargi D, Pasković I, Polić Pasković M, Glavan M, Hofman J, Huerta Lwanga E, Norgaard T, Bilková Z, Osman R, Khurshid C, Navarro I, de la Torre A, Sanz P, Ángeles Martínez M, Dias J, Mol H, Gort G, Martins Figueiredo D, Scheepers PJ, Schlünssen V, Vested A, Alaoui A, Geissen V (2023) Pesticide residues with hazard classifications relevant to non-target species including

- humans are omnipresent in the environment and farmer residences. *Environment International* 181 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2023.108280>
- Silva VAFdG (2022) [Pesticides Residues in EU Soils and Related risks](#). PhD thesis, Wageningen University. Wageningen University URL: <https://library.wur.nl/WebQuery/wurpubs/fulltext/568702>
 - Smith J (2010) A framework for assessing the sustainability of soil and groundwater remediation. CLAIRES
 - Sousa JP, Aldrich A, Axelman J, Backhaus T, Brendel S, Dorronsoro B, Duquesne S, Focks A, Holz S, Knillmann S, Pieper S, Schmied-Tobies M, Silva E, Topping C, Wipfler L, Williams J (2022) Building a European Partnership for next generation, systems-based Environmental Risk Assessment (PERA). EFSA Supporting Publications 19 (8). <https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2022.en-7546>
 - Stavi I, Bel G, Zaady E (2016) Soil functions and ecosystem services in conventional, conservation, and integrated agricultural systems. A review. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development* 36 (2). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-016-0368-8>
 - Stolte J, et al. (2016) Soil threats in Europe: status, methods, drivers and effects on ecosystem services: deliverable 2.1 RECARE project. <https://research.wur.nl/en/publications/soil-threats-in-europe-status-methods-drivers-and-effects-on-ecos>
 - TF HTAP (2021) <https://htap.org/regional-and-extra-regional-contribution-to-hg-and-pops-cec-meeting-presentations/>
 - Tóth G, Hermann T, Da Silva MR, Montanarella L (2016) Heavy metals in agricultural soils of the European Union with implications for food safety. *Environment International* 88: 299-309. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2015.12.017>
 - UNEP (2021) Regional Monitoring Report for Western Europe and other States Group (WEOG). <http://chm.pops.int/Implementation/GlobalMonitoringPlan/MonitoringReports/tabid/525/Default.aspx>
 - van Gestel CA, Mommer L, Montanarella L, Pieper S, Coulson M, Toschki A, Rutgers M, Focks A, Römbke J (2020) Soil Biodiversity: State-of-the-Art and Possible Implementation in Chemical Risk Assessment. *Integrated environmental assessment and management* 17 (3): 541-551. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ieam.4371>
 - Vanino S, Pirelli T, Di Bene C, Bøe F, Castanheira N, Chenu C, Cornu S, Feiza V, Fornara D, Heller O, Kasparinskis R, Keesstra S, Lasorella MV, Madenoğlu S, Meurer KHE, O'Sullivan L, Peter N, Piccini C, Siebielec G, Smreczak B, Thorsøe MH, Farina R (2022) Barriers and opportunities of soil knowledge to address soil challenges: Stakeholders' perspectives across Europe. *Journal of environmental management* 325 (Pt B): 116581. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.116581>
 - Vári Á, Podschun S, Erős T, Hein T, Pataki B, Iojă I, Adamescu CM, Gerhardt A, Gruber T, Dedić A, Ćirić M, Gavrilović B, Báldi A (2021) Freshwater systems and ecosystem services: Challenges and chances for cross-fertilization of disciplines. *Ambio* 51 (1): 135-151. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-021-01556-4>
 - Vazquez C, de Goede RM, Rutgers M, de Koeijer T, Creamer R (2020) Assessing multifunctionality of agricultural soils: Reducing the biodiversity trade-off. *European Journal of Soil Science* 72 (4): 1624-1639. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13019>
 - Velasquez E, Lavelle P (2019) Soil macrofauna as an indicator for evaluating soil based ecosystem services in agricultural landscapes. *Acta Oecologica* 100 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actao.2019.103446>

- Velthof G, Barot S, Bloem J, Butterbach-Bahl K, de Vries W, Kros J, Lavelle P, Olesen JE, Oenema O (2011) Nitrogen as a threat to European soil quality. The European Nitrogen Assessment 495-510. <https://doi.org/10.1017/cbo9780511976988.024>
- Vieira D, Franco A, De Medici D, Martin Jimenez J, Wojda P, Jones A (2023) Pesticides residues in European agricultural soils - Results from LUCAS 2018 soil module, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2023. <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC133940>
- Villa F, Bagstad K, Voigt B, Johnson G, Portela R, Honzák M, Batker D (2014) A Methodology for Adaptable and Robust Ecosystem Services Assessment. PLoS ONE 9 (3). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0091001>
- Wade J, et al. (2022) Rigorous, empirical, and quantitative: a proposed pipeline for soil health assessments. Soil Biology and Biochemistry 170 (108710).
- Wageningen University (2023a) Petition calls for the proposed EU Soil Health Law to be supported, but also tightened. <https://www.wur.nl/en/research-results/research-institutes/environmental-research/show-wenr/petition-calls-for-the-proposed-eu-soil-health-law-to-be-supported-but-also-tightened.htm>
- Wageningen University (2023b) Feedback of Wageningen University to the EC's consultation on the Soil Monitoring Law proposa. https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/13350-Soil-health-protecting-sustainably-managing-and-restoring-EU-soils/F3440968_en. Accessed on: 2023-12-05.
- Wood S, Blankinship J (2022) Making soil health science practical: guiding research for agronomic and environmental benefits. Soil Biology and Biochemistry 172 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2022.108776>
- Zaller J, Cantelmo C, Santos GD, Muther S, Gruber E, Pallua P, Mandl K, Friedrich B, Hofstetter I, Schmuckenschlager B, Faber F (2018) Herbicides in vineyards reduce grapevine root mycorrhization and alter soil microorganisms and the nutrient composition in grapevine roots, leaves, xylem sap and grape juice. Environmental Science and Pollution Research 25 (23): 23215-23226. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-018-2422-3>
- Zobiolo LH, Kremer RJ, Oliveira RS, Constantin J (2010) Glyphosate affects microorganisms in rhizospheres of glyphosate-resistant soybeans. Journal of Applied Microbiology 110 (1): 118-127. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2672.2010.04864.x>